

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B099
Date: 02 Jun 2005
Take Off 09:51:02 12:58:37
Landing: 11:22:34 17:12:23
Flight Time 1h31m32 4h13m46

Campaign: CLOPAP
Trials Instructions: Refuel at Newcastle
Operating Area: North Sea

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Foster	Directflight
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Keith Bower	University of Manchester
5	Mission Scientist 2	Steven Abel	Met Office
6	Flight Manager	Maureen Smith	FAAM
7	CCM2 / CCN	Stuart Heath	FAAM
8	Core Chemistry	Doug Anderson	FAAM
9	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
10	AMS	Paul Williams	University of Manchester
11	NO _x	Dave Stewart	UEA
12	NO _x Training	Andy MacDonald	UEA
13	PT _r -MS	Anne Hulse	UEA
14	WAS	Maria Nielsdottir	Leeds
15	ADA/CPI	Michael Flynn	University of Manchester
16			
17			
18			
19			
20			

Flight Track:

B099 Track 02-JUN-05

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b099
 Date: 2nd June 2005
 Project: CLOPAP
 Location: N Sea & refuel Newcastle

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
085710		Start position	0.30 kft	133	52'04.36N,0'37.48W
091334		INU	0.30 kft	133	Set to Navigate
093800		Taxy	0.31 kft	133	Start
095102		T/O	1.0 kft	241	From Cranfield
095413		ASPs	5.2 kft	352	Open
095859	101744	Run 1	11.0 kft	014	NOxy Calibrations
100545		Videos	11.0 kft	012	Start FFC & RFC
103340		Nevzorov			Zero cals
104726	105113	Profile 1	1.5 - 4.5 kft	250	QNH 1006mB
105118	105443	Profile 2	4.5 - 1.0 kft	241	1000fpm
111202		ASPs	5.5 kft	239	Close
112234		Land	0.39 kft	219	At Newcastle, refuel
112549		Stop position	0.39 kft	139	55'02.00N,1'41.93W
112733		Videos	0.39 kft	139	Pause
123750		INU	0.40 kft	139	Set to Navigate
125153		Taxy	0.40 kft	139	Start
125837		T/O	0.91 kft	241	From Newcastle
130159		ASPs	4.5 kft	103	Open
130252		Videos	4.5 kft	097	Restart FFC & RFC
131132		Nevzorov	3.2 kft	314	Cal TWC & LWC
131350	131854	Profile 3	1.2 - 5.1 kft	322	1000fpm
132137		Transit	6.5 kft	155	South to find cloud
133100	134158	Run 2	1.1 kft	153	Below cloud,QNH 1008
134526	140504	Run 3	2.1 kft	316	In cloud,
141214	143051	Run 4	1.0 kft	150	Below cloud,J-C
141528		JW & Nevz	1.2 kft	155	Nevz LWC only
142534		Precip	1.2 kft	157	
143504	144705	Run 5	2.5 kft	324	In cloud
143845		Videos	2.5 kft	326	Change tapes
145820	151028	Run 6	4.5 kft	147	
151736	152717	Run 7	5.5 kft	322	In cloud
153447	154648	Run 8	1.0 kft	156	Below cloud
155059	160255	Run 9	5.0 - 4.7 kft	336	Descend to stay in cloud
155528		Descend	4.7 kft	323	
160714	161911	Run 10	2.5 kft	160	
162409		NOxy	10.0 kft	223	Calibrations
165924		ASPs	9.4 kft	207	Close
171223		Land	0.39 kft	258	At Cranfield
171640		Stop position	0.38 kft	020	52'04.36N,0'37.48W

B099 Track 02-JUN-05

Sortie Brief: CLOPAP 3 (draft 1 : prepared by K.N. Bower)

Flight Number : B099

Date: Thursday 2nd June 2005

Mission Scientist: Keith

Bower

CLOPAP Sortie Aims:

To study the evolution of aerosol in an urban plume as it advects away from the source. To investigate the interaction of the aerosol and gases with cloud both as the aerosol/gas modifies the cloud microphysics and the cloud modifies the aerosol/gases.

CLOPAP Sortie Location:

The plan is to fly off the east coast of the UK to an area of forecasted low cloud, to sample pollution from a major urban area (TBD - such as London, Newcastle or Teeside as it advects towards and interacts with the cloud layer. Previously we have operated in the area: 54.50N 1W, 55.20N 0W, 54.40N 0.40E, 54.10N 0E, with the closest approach to the coast being around 3-4miles. This avoids danger areas and allows three to four sets of runs to be carried out in the time available (may cut the runs down to 12 minutes each, do only three sets of runs, sacrifice last profile etc to achieve required study of plume evolution) (to be discussed).

CLOPAP Sortie Summary:

The case studies will be carried out by flying a series of 100 km transects across the plume within the boundary layer, one below cloud, one in cloud and one in the lower free troposphere immediately above cloud top. Each of these sets of transects will be immediately preceded by a vertical profile extending into the lower free troposphere starting from as close to the surface as possible. These profiles will establish the vertical mixing and structure of the sampled air and establish the optimum altitudes for the following transects. This flight pattern will be repeated at intervals of about 50km to obtain up to 4 sets of transects. Although we are not aiming to perform a comprehensive Lagrangian study, this flight plan will allow us to approximately track the same air as it is advects downwind of the source region

CLOPAP Sortie Detail:

1. Take off and climb to FL 110 for transit at cruise speed to operating area (with appropriate time [~20mins] spent carrying out NO_x calibration at that level)
2. When downwind of chosen urban source, descend to minimum safe altitude below cloud. Perform a profile ascent by climbing at 1000 ft per minute to pass through cloud and to an altitude 200 ft above cloud top and/or the boundary layer top.
3. Descend to below cloud base, proceed across wind in the boundary layer until outside the plume as detected by CN counter/gases. Mission scientist to announce out of cloud transect. Perform a straight and level run below cloud base (200 ft below cloud base) across wind and of length 100 km. Expose filters* during this run and then stop filters. CCN measurements should also commence at the start of this run. Core Chemistry calibrations should be carried out at start of run (as required) and completion to be announced so that WAS sampling can begin.
4. Ascend to the middle of the cloud layer. Turn through 180 degrees. Mission Scientist to announce in cloud transect (AMS to switch to CVI inlet) and perform a straight and level run of 100 km.
5. Ascend to 200 feet above cloud top turn through 180 degrees and mission scientist to announce out of cloud transect (AMS to return to Rosemount inlet). Perform a straight and level run of length 100 km. CCN measurements should also commence at the start of this run.
6. Ascend to cruising altitude to transit to 50 km downwind and repeat steps 2 to 6
7. Continue repetitions until available flight time in science area is exhausted

8. Climb to transit level to return to home base (with appropriate time [~20mins] spent at FL100 for NO_x calibration)

Sortie Brief: CLOPAP 3 (Interaction of pollutant aerosol with warm cloud) : TWC/KNB

CLOPAP Scientific Aims

1. To investigate the evolution of an urban plume as it is advected to the northeast over East Anglia and the North Sea in cloudy conditions (if low cloud in this area). Changes in chemical speciation and the partitioning of species between the gas and particulate phases will be investigated.
2. To measure the changes in the size distribution and Cloud Condensation Nucleus (CCN) activity spectrum of the aerosol.
3. To measure changes in cloud microphysics as the aerosol properties in the plume change, particularly those of the sub-set of aerosol acting as CCN.
4. To investigate the differences in the composition of aerosol that form cloud droplets and those that remain unactivated and interstitial to the cloud, and to observe how this changes as the plume ages.
5. To investigate the role of vertical exchange between the boundary layer and the free troposphere to understand its effect on the transport of aerosols and trace gases on the cloudy plume.

CLOPAP Weather Conditions

A stratocumulus capped boundary layer forming over the sea downwind of a main source of urban air pollution. Limited convective penetration of the boundary layer top is acceptable (but not deep convection). The cloud cover should exceed 70% in the study areas.

CLOPAP Key Measurements requiring operator intervention during flight

1 Cloud Physics

- **FFSSP, 2DC, 2DP, PCASP**, Normal monitoring to ensure correct operation. Operator should note particular features of interest eg. high/low concentrations,
- **ADA* and CPI** – as above
- **CCN** - alleviator should be filled whilst in clear air either below, or upwind of the cloud layer(s) of interest. 1 sample and spectrum per run, if possible.
- **J-W LWC and Nevzorov LWC/TWC**. Where run is only partially in cloud and starts in clear, these should be zeroed/calibrated and logged by Flight Manager.
- **TWC** – initial profile should avoid cloud, if possible, to achieve good calibration.

Chemistry Measurements

WAS - 2 bottle samples per 100km flight leg unless otherwise notified by the Mission Scientist (first sample to be collected after core chemistry calibrations are completed).

NO_x, Ozone, SO₂, CO, PTRMS, Hydrogen peroxide to operate continuously.

AMS - to be operated on **Rosemount inlet** out of cloud, **CVI** inlet in cloud. The inlet should be kept closed to avoid contamination whilst the GPU is operating prior to takeoff. It may be opened once the GPU has been removed. Similarly, intake should be closed before GPU is started post-flight.

Video – the default recording setup should be forward and rear.

CCN measurements should be made by filling the alleviator in the cloud free passes. The AMS should be connected to the Rosemount inlet in clear air transects and to the CVI in cloud. The inlet should be kept closed to avoid contamination whilst the GPU is operating prior to takeoff. It may be opened once the GPU has been removed. Similarly, intake should be closed before GPU is started post-flight.

Filter samples and bottle filling should occur in clear air transects only. Three bottle samples should be filled during each boundary layer transect and 1 during the free troposphere transect. Mission scientist to indicate when in plume using CN measurements.

All other instruments should run continuously.

Mission Scientist's Log

M.Sc. K.N. Bower

CLOPAP3

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Date **02/06/05**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
(10:51:17	KNB B5T)				Take Off alt zero w 400' Sfc Wind 200°/13
		1460'			Cloud Base
		3180'			Cloud Tops
					Some Cloud at 5300' Alt ⇒ CT ~ 5000'
(10:58:16	KNB B5T ≡		09:58:00	Horace)	
(10:59:08	B5T) R1	FL110			NOXY Cool Start
09:58:59	→				AMS logging + CPC - rack not attended now
10:10:10	T	FL110	3	533N/01W	669mb -5.64°C / -1.42°C 17m/s/245° 236kts
10:12:00					TDLAS ^{not working} appears ^{no data} (Eric Chen)
					CPI, ADP working AMS/CPC ✓
10:17:44	R1 end				NOXY Cool Complete
					2DC all OK
					Latest weather Newcastle CB 800' Broken 4500'
					(SID1 & SID2 on - SID2 not op. CIPS on not op.)
10:24:10			15	54.2/0.2	Descending to 5000'
10:26:14		5000'		St.	Cloud +1.58°/12.7° 13m/s/264
		6500			larger & cloud above - CB ~ 6500
					Area ok - not above 5000' - will go to 4500'
10:29:10		4500'			Out of Cloud - none below!
10:30:26		4500'	15	56.4/0.4	7.75°C / 7.36°C 13 / 255 851mb
					Some cloud South of us - downwind Teresute 253
					Some cloud above us CB ~ 4800'
					Cloud in ahead + LMS 12 N Base.
					Also cloud below us -

Mission Scientist's Log

M.Sci K.N. BOWEN

OWPASP 3

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
		3500'			In Cloud
10:42:30		3000'			Gap in cloud - here
10:42:52		2500'	16	55.4/1.0E	CT's 2500 95/9.14 8/231
10:43:50		1400'			turning from NINE (RHT) onto SW to return to Newcastle. - headrop turn back onto control leg to N'castle.
		1400'	242	55.5/1.0	10.27/10.2°C
10:47:26	P1				Will profile to 4500' 1000'/min 935mb 2200' CT.
					(1006 level QNM) (29.1" Hg)
10:50:35		4500'	242	55.4/0.7	climbed all in clear air to 4500'
10:51:12	end P1 - start P2		240		descent from 4500' - Profile to below CB. 40°E - eastwards edge of cloud approach
10:53:36					Clear now - will continue down to 1000'
10:54:42	end P2	1000'			End P1 - turning to do - across wind transect to first extent of cloud sheet on RHS.
~ 10:58:14		1000'		55.30/25'E	Just hitting cloud sheet - near to CB turning to head back to Newcastle
11:00:34					Climbing to 5000'
11:01:47		6000'			Cloud below as again - maybe
11:03:00					7-10 mins ago NO _x (Not NO ₂) (N) Cloud s/w patchy below
11:09:31		6000'			in cloud again CB ~ 6000' + ahead - low level cloud below - patchy

Mission Scientist's Log

MS: K.N. BOWER

CLOPAP3

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
(12:17:30	KNB BST)	2500			More low cloud just east of coast.
(12:22:47	BST)				Landed.
(13:51:50	BST)				Taxi start
(13:56:10	BST)				240°/10kts sic Wind
(13:58:52	BST)				230°/10 T/D
(14:01:05	BST)	3100			3100' CB - patchy - patch cloud below
					CLOUD layer ahead
(14:04:40	BST)	4500			Thick cloud - in it
13:06:00		4500			Almost out of bottom of cloud - some new
		/			cloud below - clear patch at 4500'
13:09:44	Trans	4350			Out of CB → part A - descend to 1000
13:11:35		3120			Bank of cloud ahead - into new
		2200			
13:13:50	P3	1000			P3 to 5000
13:17:10					2mins ago CN plume - now dropping
					No cloud RMS for miles and miles ...
		5000			Perseids recovered, again - both clouds.
13:18:54	P3 end	5000			
13:22 ish	Trans	6500			- Above Cloud - going S
					CPC at 20000 - in cloud - thick
13:27:05 ish					2500 out of CB - no cloud in N box
					∅ null
13:31:00	R2	1000'			CEN spectrum
13:32:46			ISS	54.7/0.6W	CN (AMS) 20000 continuously.
13:33					14.17 / 11.36 12ms/245

NB → SE

↑ CN now 6000 - last minute or so (AMS)

Mission Scientist's Log

M Sci K. N. BOWER

CLUPAD 3

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
13:37:00		1000'			NOxY still high - show ahead
					(will have to ascend to safe alt 2700)
13:38:34					CN ~ 3000; AMS 50%, NO ₂
13:39:19	R2	1000'	154	54.3/0.3	10 miles, 3 mins to go
NW-7E 13:41:58	R2 end	1000'			R2 end
13:43:40					Rain - turning
SE-NW 13:45:26	R3	2000'			Patchy cloud - in CT's Southern end.
1008mb psatting 13:48:39	R3	2100'	324	54.4/0.3	Core Chem Cont down - WAB
					11.46/10.83 10m/s/233 933mb
13:52:36					near CB now.
13:52:10					CN low ~ 1000 cm ⁻³
					Now will be
13:55:35					12 miles to point A (30 miles from start)
					CB now gone above.
13:57:08		2100'	322	54.6/0.7W	elevated core CN ~ 10000,
14:00:00					past point A - going into N Box to
					find plume - shows only now dotted around
14:01:14					The odd increase in CN - AMS too.
					CN - Increasing Now CN ~ 15000
14:05:04	and R3				Picked up Newcastle plume - but no cloud
	Turns				to go south - steer at 50km NE - start need
					CN coming down needs for start of run
NW-SE 14:12:14	R4	1000'	158	55.3/0.5W	13.61/11.83 6m/s/226' 970mb 213kts
14:14:52	R4				passed point A
14:20:30	R4				low core - drizzle . PCASP - low 100/cm ³

Mission Scientist's Log

MS# IC. N. BOWER

CLO PAP 3

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NW-SE

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
14:22:20	R4	1000'			CO rising rapidly CN consistently
14:23:40	R4	1000'			CN just dropped by x10
14:24:00	R4	1000'	158	54.7/0.0	14.3°/10.61° 14m/s/256° 971mb 204kt
14:24:45	R4	1000'			ppt on windscreens
					less AMS mass - N° same
14:30:50	R4 end	1000'			end below cloud run - drizzle
					500/m ² ZDP end of run
		3000'			CT was 2000
					CO dropped - as we came through cloud
14:35:04	RS	2500'	329	54.4/0.3	Car Chem Calc started
					WOD ₂ drops 500 ₂ measurement - out of cloud
					OPI drops 100 ₂ - 100 ₂ - ADA ill
					CN low counts both centers
14:47:05	end RS				end of Run Right turn - to transit SOL E.
	Trans	4500			the better South we go
14:58:20	R6	4500			ppt ahead - also CB above is starting down
15:07:00	R6	4500	154	54.8/0.3	11m/s/253 7.86/8.68% 853mb 220kt
15:10:28	end R6	4500			continuing on for mass
15:11:40					SO ₂ US - dead bulbs - holding lid retracted
15:15:18					climbers @ 6500 - too high no clouds
					dropping down to 3500
15:17:36	R7	5500			ZD - very patchy down
					OPI whole range drops 100-20 ₂
15:20:10					20000 ^{AMS} CRC 4500 ^{AMS} CRC drop breaking?
					AMS nothing new after 1500

SE-NW

NW-SE

SE-NW

Mission Scientist's Log

MSci K.N. BOWEN

CLOPAP-3

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					Getting at cloud tops
					CPC ~ 5000 - pressure
15:27:17	end R7	5500		55.3/0.3	5.53 7.21 821mb 10m/s/225
					Increase in ppt - end of run.
					CPC's ↑ 20,000
					CO gone up also, O ₃ went down slowly
15:34:47	R8	1000'			Start of Run
					CB ~ 4000' RR - CB ~ 3000' ahead
15:37:21	R8	1000'	160	55.3/1.1E	COE dom cal here 971mb 1392/11.58
					13m/s/253° 194hts
15:41:00	R8	1000'			CPC dropping x2 last 3mins
			158		CB looks higher at Southern end.
15:46:32	R8	1000'	158	54.8/1.0E	13.46/12.7 970 13/252
15:46:44	end R8	1000'			descending to top a SE-NW sloping run
15:48:45		3200			CO dropped just
					CPC - low - very FAAM
15:50:59	R9	5000'			Start Run -
					No cloud beneath - Cloud above - base dropping
					we will enter cloud - and follow it down
15:53:48				55.0/1.5E	Approaching CB now - descending a little
15:56:20	R9	4700	323	55.2/1.3E	7.69/8.69 9m/s/236 848mb
16:02:55	R9 end				end run - descent to 2500
16:07:14	R10 st	2500	156	55.8/1.0	919mb 11.41/9.27, 10m/s/265
16:09:28	R10	2500			Rain,
16:19:11	end R10	2500	157	54.9/1.5E	12m/s/266° 10.93/9.44 919mb

SW-NW-SE

SE-NW

ADA 2 legs CFI ✓
 2D all OK. (sub 102)
 CCN ✓
 SD US
 NO_x Filter above main chamber ✓
 PTAMS ✓
 AMMS, CPC some strange behavior - check
 WTS ✓ (17)
 NOXY - are checked - details

CORE CHEMISTRY PRE FLIGHT LOG

PRE POWER UP	
All sample lines are connected to the rack	Y
All cylinders pressures are OK	Y
Ozone Span = 504, Offset = 50	Y

GAS PRESSURES	N ₂ (bar)	CO ₂ / Argon (bar)	CO standard (bar)
PRE FLIGHT	50	128	135
POST FLIGHT	< 10	125	134

POST POWER UP - GROUND				
Ozone Sample Flow 1 (LPM)	Ozone Sample Flow 2 (LPM)	NO _x Sample Flow (LPM)	NO _x Ozonator Flow (LPM)	SO ₂ Sample Flow (LPM)
0.3	0.4	0.071	1.113`	U/S
CO Time check against HORACE	CO Lamp Flow (ml/min)	Pressure Monochromator (bar)	Pressure Cell (Torr)	
HORACE 09:41:30 CO : 09:41:28	33.85	1.10	7.11	

ZEROS							Average
Ozone (ppbV)							
NO (ppbV)							
NO₂ (ppbV)							
NO_x (ppbV)							
SO₂ (ppbV)							

PRE FLIGHT COMMENTS

SO2 instrument is U/S (lamp burnt out)

CO ~1 min out compared to HORACE. Changing time but missing out second ":" hung the display requiring a reboot (handily times to coincide with ground to air power change). The new time after reboot had reset to midnight so another attempt was made to reset the time. Again the screen hung and another reboot was required. This time the new, correct, time had been stored (as compared above).

CORE CHEMISTRY CALIBRATION AND FLOW LOG

PREVIOUS CO CAL	Date and Flight Level	Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Cnt R (Hz)
	26 May 05 12:53:36	80.55	81.02	6526.37

Time	Flight Level	Remarks					
10:04:	FL110	First attempt at cal resulted in "Bad Cal" message. The range was 623-476. All pressures etc seemed OK so another cal was initiated almost immediately.					
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
10:01:37	FL110 (470-484)	73.56	91.01	6694.32	50.00	7.12	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		33.89	0.65	0.75	1.084	0.065	u/s
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
10:20:46	FL110 (521-530)	74.66	90.33	6744.30	50.00	7.13	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		33.90	0.65	0.75	1.077	0.065	u/s
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
13:33:56	FL011 (560-529)	77.24	85.62	6613.59	50.00	7.13	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		38.93	0.35	0.4	1.070	0.068	u/s
Time	Flight Level	Remarks					
13:36:50		NO instrument Alarm appeared for a few seconds as the Chamber temperature rose slightly above the maximum setting (51.2 deg C compared to 51.0). This happened a couple of other times later in the flight (times not noted).					
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
13:48:27	FL021 (516-528)	77.55	85.60	6638.26	50.00	7.12	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		34.15	0.35	0.45	1.079	0.068	u/s
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
14:13:22	FL010 (515-527)	78.08	85.21	6653.29	50.00	7.14	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		33.82	0.35	0.4	1.076	0.068	u/s
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgrd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
14:37:58	FL030 (517-524)	78.53	84.97	6672.77	50.00	7.13	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		33.89	0.4	0.45	1.076	0.069	u/s

Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
15:02:26	FL047 (514-523)	78.72	84.69	6667.01	50.00	7.13	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		33.89	0.05	0.05	1.085	0.069	u/s
Time	Flight Level	Remarks					
15:16:	FL060	CO cal gas value on valve switch = 522-526 therefore no cal required.					
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
15:37:16	FL100 (-)	79.73	83.82	6683.23	50.00	7.13	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		33.89	0.35	0.4	1.078	0.069	u/s
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
15:54:00	FL050 (-)	80.17	83.67	6707.90	50.00	7.14	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		33.91	0.5	0.5	1.086	0.66	u/s
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
16:10:10	FL025 (-)	80.40	83.62	6723.13	50.00	7.14	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		33.89	0.45	0.45	1.077	0.066	u/s
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample

FLIGHT NUMBER: B099	DATE: 02 Jun 2005	OPERATOR: Doug Anderson	Page 4 of 4
PROJECT: CLOPAP3			

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG

GENERAL COMMENTS

NO instrument Alarm appeared for a few seconds as the Chamber temperature rose slightly above the maximum setting (see 13:36 above). This happened a couple of other times later in the flight (times not noted).

CO cal gas leaked away from 50bar at 0900 local to empty at end of flight. Assume a leak or not properly secured connection after last refill.

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B099

Date: 08/08/05

Operator: MAP

Page 1 of 3

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
09:58:59											Start Run 1 @ FL110
10:17:44											End of Run 1
10:47:28	180	0.11	848	3000	15	300	1	20	200	12	Start Profile 1 from FL016
10:48:50	20	0.08	903	1							FL022
10:50:20	5	0.07		1							FL040
10:51:14	2	0.05									End of P1, start P2 from FL045
10:51:55	15	0.09	904	10	2	350	1				FL040
10:52:50	15	0.08		1				5			FL030
10:53:43	90	0.08		1							FL020
10:54:44	160	0.08		1							End of Profile 2 @ 1000'
13:13:52	280	0.08	1272	5							Start profile 3 from 1000'
13:14:52	350	0.08		10							FL020
13:15:58	65	0.08		5							FL030
13:17:03	35	0.08		5							FL040
13:18:38	15	0.08		5							End of Profile 3 @ FL050
13:31:01											Start Run 2 @ 1000'
13:32:00	460	0.08	1685	5							
13:34:00	100	0.08		5							
13:36:00	350	0.09	1686	5							
13:38:00	400	0.10		5							
13:40:00	400	0.10		5							
13:42:01											End of Run 2
13:45:27											Start Run 3 @ 2100'
13:46:00	170	0.2	1738	1000	1	800	1	60	800	1	
13:48:00	300	0.10	1826	1000							
13:50:00	170	0.23	2100	1000	2	800	1				
13:52:00	205	0.09	2117	10							
13:54:00	300	0.08	2121	5							
13:56:00	230	0.08		5							
13:58:00	20	0.07		2							
14:00:00	10	0.07		1							
14:02:00	50	0.07		10							
14:04:00	150	0.08		10	1						
14:05:07											End of Run 3

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B099

Date: 08/08/05

Operator: MAP

Page 2 of 3

G.M.T.	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
DRS Time	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
14:12:16											Start Run 4 @ 1000'
14:13:00	180	0.08	2121	10							
14:15:00	160	0.08		5							
14:17:00	65	0.08		5							
14:19:00	45	0.08		10	1			200	800	1	
14:21:00	170	0.07	2122	5							
14:23:00	80	0.07		2							
14:25:00	70	0.07		5				25			
14:27:00	250	0.09		10				225	800	1	
14:29:00	400	0.12	2125	10	1			340	800	1	Overheat on FFSSP
14:30:51											End of Run 4
14:35:06											Start Run 5 @ 2500'
14:36:00	180	0.10	2143	2000	3	600	1	600	800	1	
14:38:00	170	0.11	2149	10	1	600	1	400	1000	1	
14:40:00	140	0.10	2153	10	1	600	1	800	600	1	
14:42:00	130	0.08	2154	10				40	600	1	
14:44:00	10	0.07	2155	5	1			60	800	1	
14:46:00	80	0.07		10							
14:47:06											End of Run 5
14:58:20											Start Run 6 @ 4500'
14:59:00	40	0.09	2162	20	3	600	1	400	600	1	
15:01:00	70	0.13	2164	20	1	600	1	200			
15:03:00	90	0.08		5				60	800	1	
15:05:00	5	0.25	2166	30	4	800	1	1000	800	1	
15:07:00	70	0.45	2173	1000	35	400	1	500	800	1	
15:09:00	30	0.16	2178	10	2	800	1	1000	400	12	
15:10:29											End of Run 6
15:17:38											Start Run 7 @ 5500'
15:18:00	11	0.34	2189	1000	3	425	1	1300	600	1	
15:20:00	30	0.36	2200	80	35	250	1	800	400	12	
15:22:00	40	0.34	2202	20	5	575	1	1000	400	12	
15:24:00	20	0.56	2206	20	5	500	1	400	800	12	
15:26:00	6	0.15	2213	1000	6	600	1	900	1600	1	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B099

Date: 08/08/05

Operator: MAP

Page 3 of 3

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
15:27:19											End of Run 7
15:34:50											Start Run 8 @ 1000'
15:35:00	180	0.07	2252	5							
15:37:00	500	0.08		5				30			
15:39:00	180	0.09		5	1			400	400	12	
15:41:00	190	0.09	2253	10	1			300	400	12	
15:43:00	200	0.11	2254	10	1			340	1800	1	
15:45:00	240	0.09	2257	10	5	500	1	600	1000	1	
15:46:50											End of Run 8
15:51:01											Start Run 9 @ 5000'
15:52:00	10	0.43	2274	10	1	800	1	160	600	1	
15:54:00	5	0.43	2277	100	10	700	1	2000	600	1	
15:56:00	25	0.43	2286	100	3	700	1	925	1600	1	
15:58:00	45	0.25	2294	80	1	800	1	725	600	1	
16:00:00	45	0.14	2295	15	5	450	1	500	600	1	
16:02:00	50	0.13	2298	70	5	450	1	325	400	1	
16:02:57											End of Run 9
16:07:16											Start Run 10 @ 2500'
16:08:00	160	0.09	2300	10	1	600	1	300	400	12	
16:10:00	230	0.08	2301	20				60	400	12	
16:12:00	120	0.08	2303	15	1	450	1	325	600	1	
16:14:00	55	0.08	2304	10	1	500	1	300	600	1	
16:16:00	65	0.13		10	1	500	1	350	4000	1	
16:18:00	45	0.07	2306	5	1	800	1	100	1600	1	
16:19:13											End of Run 10
	SEADAS Time offset = 0										
	FFSSP Failed once due to overheat, switched off for short period and again for a short period later when not in a Run										
	PCASP Flow rate = 0.9 CC/ sec										
	PCASP Activity set to 1% due to error in Activity counts										

Flight No B099

CCNC LOG

Exp. CLOPAP

Date 2/06/05

Page 1 of 2

ALLEVIATOR GMT		Height 1000 ft	TEMP INLET	STATIC						REMARKS
ON	OFF			1	2	3	4	5		
133141	133228			1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5		
				0.45					S	Baseline
				805					D	Drop out
				2411					B	
				2411					R	
				995.2					P	
133141	133228	1000ft	30.62	0.44	0.66	0.98	1.29	1.90	S	
			30.50	732	1318	816	3161	712	D	
			30.01	437	437	451	451	460	B	
			30.01	2289	2323	2390	2428	2430	R	
			29.52	995.2	995.2	995.5	995.3	995.1	P	
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5		
14214	141255	1000ft	29.52	0.45	0.65	0.98	1.29	1.88	S	
			29.95	706	483	1522	1608	1724	D	
			29.28	332	332	337	345	344	B	
			29.46	2459	2457	2453	2454	2456	R	
			29.11	995.1	995.1	995.1	995.1	995.1	P	
			29.25	0.45	0.66	0.99	1.28	1.88	S	
			29.24	761	994	1242	1428	2342	D	
			29.14	333	333	334	333	335	B	
			28.65	2450	2447	2443	2437	2429	R	
			28.54	995.1	995.1	995.1	995.0	995.1	P	
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5		
150110	150150	4700ft	29.02	0.45	0.66	1.01	1.28	1.89	S	
			29.69	545	672	691	757	1037	D	
			29.06	335	338	338	330	350	B	
			29.69	2366	2371	2376	2373	2373	R	
			29.01	995.1	995.1	995.2	995.1	995.1	P	
153517	153550	1000ft	29.39	0.45	0.65	0.98	1.30	1.89	S	
				1399	1689	2666	2718	3169	D	
			29.02	366	366	366	366	367	B	
			29.33	2431	2436	2437	2442	2449	R	
			28.64	2433	2436		995.1	995.1	P	
				995.1	995.1	995.1				

Air Sample ↑

Flight No B099

CCNC LOG

Exp. CLO9AP

Date 02/06/05

Page 2 of 2

ALLEVIATOR GMT		Height	TEMP INLET	STATIC					REMARKS
ON	OFF			1	2	3	4	5	
		1000ft	28.90	1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
			29.14	0.45	0.67	0.99	1.28	1.87	S
			28.78	964	1144	2105	2951	4092	D
			28.47	354	354	355	359	361	B
			28.57	2448	2456	2454	2458	2464	R
				995.0	995.1	995.1	995.1	995.1	P
160714	160759	2500ft	29.46	0.45	0.65	0.98	1.28	1.88	S
			29.54	979	897	1183	1495	2526	D
			29.21	388	376	371	371	361	B
			28.95	2487	2489	2488	2490	2493	R
			28.74	995.1	995.0	995.1	995.2	995.1	P
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
			29.02	0.45	0.65	1.01	1.50	1.87	S
			28.87	692	741	956	2374	2102	D
			28.81	349	349	347	345	345	B
			28.55	2484	2788	2487	2485	2485	R
			28.54	995.1	995.0	995.1	995.1	995.1	P
									S
									D
									B
									R
									P
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
									S
									D
									B
									R
									P
									S
									D
									B
									R
									P

SAME as
SAMPLE
AS LAST

SAME
SAMPLE
AS LAST

WAS Sampling Summary

Flight Number: B099

Campaign Name: CLOPAP

Date: 06/06/2005

Operator: M. Nielsdottir (UEA)

Bottle Start Fill Time	Bottle End Fill Time	Bottle Number	Comments	Final Pressure (bar)
13:31:00			Start run 2 at 1000 ft	
13:35:04	13:36:04	3		3.33
13:37:57	13:38:57	2	Did not catch the dirtiest air as core chemistry was calibrating	3.33
13:45:26			Start run 3 at 2100 ft	
13:49:32	13:50:32	1	In cloud for part of the run	3.32
13:52:38	13:53:38	15		3.32
14:05:04			End run 3	
14:12:14			Start run 4 at 1000 ft	
14:14:57	14:15:57	13	Below cloud	3.34
14:20:08	14:21:08	10		3.32
14:30:51			End run 4	
14:35:04			Start run 5 at 2000 ft	
14:41:10	14:42:10	14		3.31
14:46:39	14:47:39	12		3.32
14:47:05			End run 5	
14:38:20			Start run 6 at 4500 ft	
15:03:31	15:04:31	11	Below cloud	3.24
15:10:25	15:11:25	8		3.24
15:10:28			End run 6	
15:17:36			Start run 7 at 5500 ft	
15:19:44	15:20:44	6	In cloud	3.21
15:24:06	15:25:06	5		3.21
15:27:17			End run 7	
15:34:47			Start run 8 at 1000 ft	
15:38:23	15:39:23	9		3.33

15:42:12	15:43:12	7		3.34
15:46:48			End run 8	
15:50:50			Start run 9 at 5000 ft	
15:59:15	16:00:15	4		3.23
16:03:33	16:04:33	16	Descending to 2000 ft	
16:02:55			End run 9	
16:07:14			Start run 10 at 2500 ft	
16:11:46	16:12:46	17		3.31
16:15:23	16:16:23	18		3.32
16:19:11			End run 10	

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B099**

Date: 02/06/05

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU		Y	Probes		
GPS		Y	FFSSP	Y	Y
Satcom C		Y	PCASP	Y	Y
Satcom H		Y	2D-P	Y	Y
<u>Thermometers</u>			2D-C	Y	Y
De-Iced Temp		Y	Cloudscope	N	N
Non De-Iced		Y	SID 1	Y	Y
Heimann	N		SID 2	Y	Y
<u>Hygrometers</u>					
G. Eastern		Y	HVPS	N	
J. Williams		Y	CIP25	Y	N
Nevzorov		Y	CIP100	Y	N
TWC		Y			
FWVS	Y	N	Racks:		
<u>Radiometers</u>			INC	Y	N
Upper Clear	Y	Y	CCN / CNC	Y	Y
“ Red	Y	Y	CVI	Y	N
“ Silicon	Y	Y			
“ JO1D	Y	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>		
Lower Clear	Y	Y	PSAP	Y	N
“ Red	Y	Y	Nephelometer	N	
“ Silicon	Y	Y	Filters	Y	N
“ JO1D	N		AMS	Y	Y
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS	N				
MARSS	N				
DEIMOS	N		<u>Others:</u>		
ARIES	N		NIR TDLAS	Y	Y
SWS	N		2BT O3	Y	N
<u>Chemistry</u>			VACC	Y	N
Ozone	Y	Y	PEROXIDE	Y	Y
ECGC	N		Formaldehyde	Y	N
NOX	Y	Y	ADA	Y	Y
CO	Y	Y	CPI	Y	Y
ORAC	Y	N	NOxy	Y	Y
PAN	Y	N	PTRMS	Y	Y
PERCA	N	N	Bag Sampling	Y	N
WAS	Y	Y			

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B099

Date: 02/06/05

Instruments

1. Video – RFC display out of focus. Inboard display switches off .
2. Mission Scientist's laptop – needs new ethernet cable, the connector at the pc end is falling off.
3. TDLAS – No data coming through to pc after take-off. Tried rebooting pc and checked serial link. 28V CB found to be not made,
4. Upper Pyrgeometer – Zero signal following radiance signal exactly.
5. Ethernet cables – need to carry more spares. PTRms borrowed Core Console spare, none available for WAS pc.
6. HORACE – data dropout ~ 1436 for about 1min. Coincided with Fltsumm locking up. At 1438 Buffer overflow writing to hard disc and write failure on optical disc. New file opened on optical disc for gpsdat.dat Error count on hard disk=3, 15 on optical.
7. SO2 u/s, lamp blown.
8. NOX – occasional flutters above max chamber temp but otherwise okay.
9. Cloud Physics - FFSSP 1 overheat & SID2 - 3 known problems, other probes okay.
10. HORACE – FWVS log

Non Core Instruments Status

CPI – fine all flight

ADA – data for 1st couple of runs but nothing significant after that.

PTRms – fine.

CCN – problem initially with baseline but apart from a couple of spurious readings okay.

AMS – fine

WAS – fine, 17 bottles filled

NOxy – 1 of the NOY channels very sensitive otherwise okay.

Peroxide – problem early on with zero channel flatlining but looked okay after departing Newcastle.

Aircraft

1. Nil sig.

Satcom H – 1 call made by Keith Bower

At 12Z on 2/ 6/2005, from 00Z on 2/ 6/2005
Cloud cover and PMSL Operational

SSFM weather summary for S00003240 for 02/06/2005

Temperatures and precipitation

Wind speed and direction at 10 m

